

Tracing cuneiform using Inkscape

Inkscape is one of the most popular vector graphics editor, and it is open-source.

Important concepts

Vector graphic: Image generated by means of a series of position points stored in a computer. The image is generated anew with each new scale, which means that it is never pixelated. Typical vector graphics formats are SVG (Inkscape's native), EPS and PDF.

Nodes: Each of the points of a line stored in a computer. The curvature of the line can be modified by means of the **handles** attached to each point.

Paths: Each of the lines between nodes generated by a computer using the “nodes” as the basis. The **Bézier curve** is a special kind of path.

0. First download the program from <https://inkscape.org/> (current version: 0.92.3 [March 2018])

Important shortcuts in Inkscape

s	Selector tool (or hit space, again to go back to the tool)
n	Node tool
b	Bezier Tool
p	Pen Tool
Shift + b	Break path at selected node

1. BASIC TRACING

- 1.1. Create a new file on Inkscape, and simply drag the file of the tablet's photo into Inkscape.

- 1.2. Go to the Layers panel.

- 1.2.1. Lock the original layer, and rename it to “image.” Reduce “Opacity” to ca. 50% (Image 1.2.1).

- 1.2.2. Create a new layer, rename it to “signs.”

- 1.2.3. Create two further layers: rename one to “border” and the other one to “damage.”

- 1.2.4. Select the “signs” layer and click on the image.

- 1.3. Set up the tools by double clicking on each of them (see image 1.3). The following [Image 1.2.1](#) are recommended, although you might prefer to alter them (table 1.3):

Pen (bézier): Signs and non-preserved borders: **0.500 px** (note, for preserved borders, use **2 px**)
Pencil: For damage dots, **0.500px** (ctrl+click size: **0.25** times current stroke width, see adjoining image)

Table 1.3

Image 1.3

1.4. Resize photograph: Make sure that the photograph that you use as the basis has a ruler in it. Click on the Measurement tool (📏), shortcut: “M”) and set it to cm on the top panel. Then click at the beginning of the cm mark of the ruler and drag the mouse, pressing Ctrl at the same time, until the end of the cm mark (see image 1.4). That way you can control the scale at which you want to make the copy. For instance, for a 1½ : 1 scale, the Measurement tool should mark 1.50 cm for each cm mark. If the ruler is too big or to small, simply resize the image until you obtain the desired scale.

Image 1.3

1.5. The most important tool for the initial drawing is the **bézier** curve (shortcut: “b”). We will use the bézier tool for the smooth edges of the tablet and for the initial drawing of the wedges.

1.5.1. For the drawing of the **preserved** (i.e., smooth) **edges** of a tablet, click at the beginning of the edge, click again at the end, and leave the mouse's right button pressed while dragging the vector until the line has the desired curvature. Then press Enter or right click (see image 1.5.1)

1.5.1.1. To draw another smooth edge, you can start at the same node of the old path simply by starting the new curve on it.

1.5.1.2. To resize preserved edges (recommended setting: 2px, see table 1.3), go to the "Fill and Stroke" (shortcut: Shift+Ctrl+F) panel, to "Stroke size", set it in px, enter the desired value, and press Enter.

1.5.1.3. To draw **non-smooth edges**, see below 1.7.

1.5.2. For the initial drawing of the wedges, begin the drawing by the head of the wedge. To draw it, click once at the beginning of the head, then click again at the end and hold the mouse button while moving it until the line acquires the desired curvature (image 1.5.2). Then press Enter or right click.

Image

Image 1.5.2

1.5.2.1. Begin then the new curve of the head by first clicking on the last node (see image 1.5.2.1). Repeat the process.

- 1.6. **Straight lines** can be drawn with the bezier tool, first clicking at the beginning of the line and then clicking again (without dragging) at the end.
- 1.7. For drawing **non-straight** and **non-smoothly-curved lines** (i.e., **non-preserved** parts of the edges), you can use several bézier-curves in sequence, ones starting at the others' nodes. However, it might be easier to use the pencil tool (shortcut: "p")
 - 1.7.1. Select it and trace the non-preserved edge. It will look very weird (see image 1.7.1) because at the beginning we set the pencil tool only for drawing damage points (on which see below 1.9)
 - 1.7.2. To solve this, the easiest way is to select and copy (Ctrl+C) one already drawn bézier path, then select the line drawn with the pencil tool and "paste style" (Shift+Ctrl+V), see image 1.7.2.
 - 1.7.2.1. To make the line thus obtained smoother, go to Path > Simplify (shortcut: Ctrl+L).
 - 1.7.2.2. To make it even smoother, after 1.7.2.1 double click on the path to go to node view, select all the nodes (shortcut: Ctrl+A) and press the button "Make selected nodes auto-smooth" at the top panel ().

1.8. In some signs there will be **intersections** between the wedges. The copy looks considerably more elegant if you clean these.

1.8.1. To do so, select the **node** tool (**n** or double click on the path) and click twice on each of the two sides of the intersected line to create two new nodes (see image 1.8.1).

1.8.2. Then select the newly created nodes (keep Shift pressed), and press **Shift + b** to cut the path between them. Select then the path between the two new nodes, and press **Delete** (image 1.8.2).

1.9. To draw **damage dots**, select the tool **pencil** (**p**) and click while pressing the key **Ctrl**.

2. SPEEDING UP THE PROCESS

2.1. Once you know how to copy with Inkscape using the Bezier curve, let's learn a few tricks to make the process faster.

2.2. First, make sure that the option “When scaling objects, scale the stroke width by the same proportion” is unchecked. You can find it at the top menu (see image 2.2).

2.3. The basic trick is to copy and paste already drawn signs to use them as the basis for new signs. An important shortcut is **Ctrl + D** (for duplicate): when a sign is selected, Ctrl+D will create an exact copy of the selected object, place it in front of it and select it automatically. See table 2.3 for other

Important shortcuts	
Ctrl+Alt+V	Paste in place
Ctrl+Caps+V	Paste style of copied object into selected object

Table 2.3

important shortcuts

2.4. Whenever the new signs have different sizes, simply resize them.

2.5. If you are adapting old copies, you might want to resize the damage dots. To do so:

2.5.1. Select all dots you want to resize.

2.5.2. Go to Object > Transform (Shortcut: Shift+Ctrl+M)

2.5.3. In the dialogue in the left hand side, check “Scale proportionally” and “Apply to each object individually”

2.5.4. Enter the scale (e.g. 50%) and click “Apply”. Voilà!

3. SAVING AND SHARING YOUR COPIES

Once you are finished with your copy, you might want to send it to the printers.

3.1. Inkscape’s native format, **SVG** (for “Scalable Vector Graphic”), is one of the most popular formats for vector graphics. However, very few journals will accept a submission of a copy in the SVG format, and still fewer will be able to handle a SVG file correctly.

3.2. The easiest way to save your copy as a vector graphic is to go to File > Save As (shortcut: Shift+Ctrl+S) and choose **PDF** (“Portable Document Format”). Typesetters can then either import the PDF into your manuscript or else export the PDF into any bitmap graphic format and use it for your article.

3.2.1. When you save your file as a PDF, make sure that the “Photo” layer is invisible by clicking on the eye icon in the layers menu (see image 3.2.1)

3.3. Typesetters might demand a **bitmap** file from you. If that is the case, Inkscape supports exporting to **PNG** format (“Portable Network Graphic”)

3.3.1. First, go to “Document Properties” (shortcut: Shift+Ctrl+D) and click on the box to the right of “Background color” (image 3.3.1). Make sure that the transparency (“A”) is set to 255 (i.e., the maximum to the right). This will ensure that the background of the PNG file is not transparent.

3.3.2. Then go to “Export PNG Image” (shortcut: Shift+Ctrl+E), select “Drawing” (so that only the drawing is exported), write the required DPI (“Dots Per Inch”, typically 600), select where to save the file (“Export As...”) and click “Export”. Voilà!

Image 3.2.1

Image 3.3.1